

HOMOGENIZATION CREEP ANALYSIS OF PLAIN-WOVEN GFRP LAMINATES

T. Matsuda, K. Nakata, M. Kawai

Department of Engineering Mechanics and Energy, University of Tsukuba
1-1-1 Tennodai, Tsukuba 305-8573, Japan
matsuda@kz.tsukuba.ac.jp (T. Matsuda)

SUMMARY

In-plane creep behavior of plain-woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates subjected to a constant stress is analyzed using the time-dependent homogenization theory. It is shown that the in-plane creep behavior of the plain-woven GFRP laminates exhibits marked anisotropy, and is strongly affected by their laminate configurations.

Keywords: Homogenization; Creep; Plain-Woven Laminate; Laminate Configuration

INTRODUCTION

Plain-woven laminates made of plain fabrics and polymeric materials have been used in many high-end industrial products such as components of aircraft and vehicles, and blades of wind power generators. In these situations, plain-woven laminates can be subjected to high stress and high temperature, bringing about creep deformation of the plain-woven laminates. Thus, creep analysis of plain-woven laminates is now an extremely important subject area. Such analysis, however, generally involves difficulties because plain-woven laminates have considerably complex internal structures comprised of fiber bundles and matrix materials (see Fig. 1), and these materials have completely different creep properties, respectively.

To analyze the inelastic behavior of plain-woven laminates with the above-mentioned complex internal structures, a multi-scale simulation technique based on the mathematical homogenization theory [1,2] is highly advantageous, because it enables us to analyze the microscopic stress and strain distributions in laminates as well as the macroscopic behavior of the laminates themselves. In fact, this technique has been already applied to microscopic failure propagation analyses of plain-woven GFRP laminates subjected to an in-plane on-axis load [3-5]. In addition, the present authors [6] also performed elastic-viscoplastic analysis of plain-woven GFRP laminates using the time-dependent homogenization theory developed by the authors.[7,8] However, so far there is no report in which the creep analysis of plain-woven laminates has been done using the homogenization theory.

In this study, homogenization creep analysis of plain-woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates subjected to a constant stress is performed using the time-dependent homogenization theory [7,8]. Moreover, the effects of laminate configurations of plain fabrics on the creep behavior of the laminates are also analyzed.

HOMOGENIZATION THEORY FOR PLAIN-WOVEN LAMINATES

Domain of Analysis

In this study, two patterns of laminate configurations of plain fabrics, i.e. in-phase and out-of-phase, are employed as internal structures of plain-woven laminates [3-6]. The in-phase laminate configuration has no offset of plain fabrics in the y_1 - and y_2 -directions (Fig. 1(a)), while the out-of-phase laminate configuration has the phase shift of plain fabrics by π in the y_1 - and y_2 -directions (Fig. 1(b)). As shown in the previous paper [6], the plain-woven laminates with the above two laminate configurations have point-symmetric internal structures and the point-symmetry is able to be utilized as a boundary condition for boundary value problems⁹, so that we can reduce the domain of analysis. This method is briefly explained in the following two paragraphs.

First, for an in-phase laminate configuration, a unit cell Y of the laminate is defined as shown by the dashed lines in Fig. 1(a). In addition, a basic cell A is also defined as indicated by the solid lines in Fig. 1(a). A careful look at the figure reveals that the internal structure of the laminate has point-symmetry with respect to the centers of lateral facets of A , which are denoted by the open circles in Fig. 1(a). Perturbed velocity in the laminate, therefore, distributes point-symmetrically with respect to these points. By contrast, the perturbed velocity at the top and bottom facets of A satisfies the Y -periodicity because the internal structure is periodic with respect to A in the y_3 -direction (stacking direction). The use of the point-symmetry and Y -periodicity of perturbed velocity as a boundary condition with the previous results⁹ enables us to take A as the domain of analysis and to derive the boundary value problems (4) and (5) shown in section 2.2.

Fig. 1. Unit cells Y and basic cells A of plain-woven laminates; (a) in-phase, (b) out-of-phase.

Next, with an out-of-phase laminate configuration, a unit cell Y is taken as indicated by the dashed lines in Fig. 1(b). The unit cell has twice the volume of the in-phase laminate configuration, but the same basic cell A is again defined as shown by the solid lines in Fig. 1(b). As indicated in the figure, the internal structure of the laminate has point-symmetry with respect to the centers of the top and bottom facets as well as the lateral facets of A , i.e., the centers of all the boundary facets of A , which are denoted by the open circles in Fig. 1(b). Thus, the perturbed velocity in the laminate distributes point-symmetrically with respect to these points. Employing the point-symmetric distribution of perturbed velocity as a boundary condition, the same boundary value problems (4) and (5) as for the in-phase laminate configuration are obtained.

Homogenization Theory

The basic cell A , mentioned above, is then employed as the domain of analysis for the time-dependent homogenization theory [7,8]. Let us consider that a plain-woven laminate is subjected to macroscopically uniform load and exhibits infinitesimal deformation both macroscopically and microscopically. The constituents of the laminate are assumed to have elastic-creep properties and obey the following constitutive equation:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijkl} (\dot{\epsilon}_{kl} - \beta_{kl}), \quad (1)$$

where $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$ and $\dot{\epsilon}_{kl}$ indicate microscopic stress and strain rates, respectively, c_{ijkl} and β_{kl} signify elastic stiffness and creep function, respectively, satisfying $c_{ijkl} = c_{jikl} = c_{ijlk} = c_{klij}$ and $\beta_{kl} = \beta_{lk}$. Then, the evolution equation of microscopic stress $\dot{\sigma}_{ij}$, and the relationship between macroscopic stress rate $\dot{\Sigma}_{ij}$ and strain rate \dot{E}_{kl} are derived as follows [6-9]:

$$\dot{\sigma}_{ij} = c_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \dot{E}_{kl} - c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}), \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{\Sigma}_{ij} = \langle c_{ijpq} (\delta_{pk} \delta_{ql} + \chi_{p,q}^{kl}) \rangle \dot{E}_{kl} - \langle c_{ijkl} (\beta_{kl} - \varphi_{k,l}) \rangle, \quad (3)$$

where δ_{ij} denotes Kronecker's delta, $(\)_{,i}$ indicates the differentiation with respect to Cartesian coordinates y_i ($i=1, 2, 3$), and $\langle \# \rangle = |A|^{-1} \int_A \# dA$. Here, $|A|$ stands for the volume of A . Moreover, χ_i^{kl} and φ_i are the characteristic functions determined by solving the following boundary value problems:

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \chi_{p,q}^{kl} v_{i,j} dA = - \int_A c_{ijkl} v_{i,j} dA, \quad (4)$$

$$\int_A c_{ijpq} \varphi_{p,q} v_{i,j} dA = \int_A c_{ijkl} \beta_{kl} v_{i,j} dA, \quad (5)$$

where v_i denotes an arbitrary velocity field satisfying the point-symmetry with respect to the centers of boundary facets of A or the Y -periodicity. The above problems are solved using FEM based on the boundary condition described in the previous section. In

consequence, compared with the case of using unit cells, the domain of analysis is reduced to 1/4 and 1/8 for the in- and out-of-phase laminate configurations, respectively.

CREEP ANALYSIS OF PLAIN-WOVEN GFRP LAMINATES

Analysis Conditions

Using the present method, in-plane creep deformations of plain-woven glass fiber/epoxy laminates subjected to a constant stress (60MPa) were analyzed under the macroscopic plane stress condition. First, the laminates were elongated at a constant strain rate (10^{-5}s^{-1}) until accomplishing the prescribed creep stress. After that, the stress was held constant for five hours. Defining an off-axis angle as the angle between a loading direction and the warp direction, four kinds of off-axis angles, i.e. $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$ were considered. Two types of laminate configurations stated in the previous section, i.e., the in- and out-of-phase laminate configurations were assumed.

Basic Cell

The basic cell and its finite element mesh used in the present analysis is illustrated in Fig 2, which is the same as in the previous paper [6]. The cell was discretized into finite elements using eight-node isoparametric elements (1,624 elements, 1,995 nodes).

Material Properties

Fiber bundles were regarded as glass fiber/epoxy unidirectional composites and as linear elastic materials. The material properties of fiber bundles were calculated using the homogenization theory [1,2] on the assumption that the fiber volume fraction was 75 % and that the bundles had a hexagonal fiber array. The elastic properties of the glass fibers and epoxy used in the calculation are listed in Table 1. By contrast, the matrix (epoxy) was regarded as an isotropic elastic-creep material and to obey the following constitutive equation:

Fig. 2. Basic cell and finite element mesh; (a) full view with dimensions in mm, (b) fiber bundles in basic cell.

Table 1. Material constants [6].

Glass fiber	$E_f = 80 \times 10^3$	$\nu_f = 0.30$	
Epoxy	$E_m = 5.0 \times 10^3$	$\nu_m = 0.35$	$\dot{\varepsilon}_0^p = 10^{-5}$
	$n = 20$	$g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p) = (\bar{\varepsilon}^p)^{0.50} + 24.5/2.5\bar{\varepsilon}^p$	

MPa (stress), mm/mm (strain), s (time).

$$\dot{\varepsilon}_{ij} = \frac{1+\nu_m}{E_m} \dot{\sigma}_{ij} - \frac{\nu_m}{E_m} \dot{\sigma}_{kk} \delta_{ij} + \frac{3}{2} \dot{\varepsilon}_0^p \left[\frac{\sigma_{eq}}{g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)} \right]^n \frac{s_{ij}}{\sigma_{eq}}, \quad (6)$$

where E_m , ν_m and n signify material constants, $g(\bar{\varepsilon}^p)$ stands for a hardening function depending on equivalent viscoplastic strain $\bar{\varepsilon}^p$, $\dot{\varepsilon}_0^p$ indicates a reference strain rate, s_{ij} denotes deviatoric part of σ_{ij} , and $\sigma_{eq} = \left[\frac{3}{2} s_{ij} s_{ij} \right]^{1/2}$. These constants are listed in Table 1. Incidentally, material constants in Table 1 are the same as in the previous paper [6].

Results of Analysis

Figure 3 shows macroscopic creep curves of the plain-woven GFRP laminates at a constant creep stress, 60MPa, with four kinds of off-axis angles, $\theta = 0^\circ, 15^\circ, 30^\circ, 45^\circ$. First, it is seen from the figure that the creep strain is hardly observed at $\theta = 0^\circ$ (on-axis loading). Similarly, considerably small creep strain occurs at $\theta = 15^\circ$. However, with $\theta = 30^\circ$, the creep strain suddenly increases and at $\theta = 45^\circ$, it further increases and reaches the maximum. These results are obtained irrespective of the laminate configurations, suggesting that the plain-woven GFRP laminates have marked in-plane anisotropy with respect to macroscopic creep behavior.

Fig. 3. Creep strain versus creep time relations of plain-woven GFRP laminates

Next, comparing the results of the in-phase laminate configuration with those of the out-of-phase one, there is little difference in the creep strain at $\theta = 0^\circ$ and 15° . By contrast, the difference between the two laminate configurations becomes clear at $\theta = 30^\circ$ and 45° . Especially, at $\theta = 45^\circ$, the creep strain of the out-of-phase laminate configuration is more than twice as large as that of the in-phase one. It is thus shown that there is significant dependence of the creep behavior of plain-woven GFRP laminates on the laminate configurations.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study, creep analysis of GFRP plain-woven laminates subjected to a constant stress was performed using the time-dependent homogenization theory developed by the present authors. Employing a basic cell as the domain of analysis, two types of laminate configurations, i.e., in- and out-of-phase laminate configurations were considered. It was shown that in-plane off-axis creep behavior of the plain-woven GFRP laminates exhibited marked in-plane anisotropy. It was also shown that the laminate configurations of plain fabrics had significant effects on the creep behavior of the plain-woven GFRP laminates.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors acknowledge support, in part, from the Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Japan under a Grant-in-Aid for Young Scientists (B) (No. 20760064).

References

1. A. Bensoussan, J.L. Lions and G. Papanicolaou, *Asymptotic Analysis for Periodic Structures* (North-Holland Publishing Company, Amsterdam, 1978).
2. E. Sanchez-Palencia, *Non-Homogeneous Media and Vibration Theory, Lecture Notes in Physics, No. 127* (Springer-Verlag, Berlin, 1980).
3. N. Takano, M. Zako and S. Sakata, *Trans. Jpn. Soc. Mech. Eng.* **A61**, 1038 (1995), (in Japanese).
4. N. Takano, Y. Uetsuji, Y. Kashiwagi and M. Zako, *Model. Simul. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **7**, 207 (1999).
5. V. Carvelli and C. Poggi, *Compos.* **A32**, 1425 (2001).
6. T. Matsuda, Y. Nimiya, N. Ohno and M. Tokuda, *Compos. Struct.* **79**, 493 (2007).
7. X. Wu and N. Ohno, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* **36**, 4991 (1999).
8. N. Ohno, X. Wu and T. Matsuda, *Int. J. Mech. Sci.* **42**, 1519 (2000).
9. N. Ohno, T. Matsuda and X. Wu, *Int. J. Solids Struct.* **38**, 2867 (2001).